

10. E. WILDER SMITH, *U.S.* 3, 127, 410 (Cl. 260-307); *Chem. Abst.*, 1964, 61, 3118.
11. S. GIRI and H. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1966, 43, 129.
12. P. N. BHARGAVA and K. I. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 88, 77.
13. M. S. GIBSON, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, 18, 1377-80.

Monomethylglyoxime Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Chlorides

V. H. GALGALI and D. D. KHANOLKAR

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad.

Manuscript received 30 August 1975; revised 19 September 1975; accepted 8 October 1975.

α -DIOXIMES like dimethylglyoxime, α -furyl dioxime etc. are well known analytical reagents. The literature survey shows that not much work has been done on the use of unsymmetrical glyoximes in preparation of metal complexes. The present communication deals with preparation of solid coordination complexes of monomethylglyoxime with copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) chlorides and their characterisation by elemental analysis, I.R. and electronic absorption spectra and magnetic susceptibility.

Experimental

The metal salts used were of analytical reagent grade. The ligand and the metal complexes were prepared by the following methods: Monomethylglyoxime (MMG) was prepared by the method given in the literature¹, m.p. 154° (Found: N, 27.42%; Calcd. for C₃H₆O₂N₂: N, 27.50%). Solid metal complexes were prepared by refluxing alcoholic solution of metal chlorides and the ligand in 1:2 molar ratio. In preparing Co(II) complex, it was necessary to raise the pH of the solution to 8.0-8.5 pH with alcoholic ammonia solution. The complexes were purified by washing with alcohol and ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂.

The complexes were decomposed with HCl and metal ion contents were estimated using standard EDTA solution. Nitrogen was estimated by micro-Kjeldahl's method. The chloride content in copper and cobalt complexes was estimated as silver chloride. Molar conductances were measured on LKB-3216 conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were done at TIFR, Bombay in the temperature range 300°K to 80°K on Gouy balance using mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) as a calibrant

Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. IR absorption spectra were recorded in nujol mull with Perkin-Elmer infracord 137-E. Diffuse reflectance, U.V. and visible spectra were measured on Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data on electronic spectra, magnetic susceptibility and solution molar conductivity of the complexes are set out in Table 1.

Copper(II) complex:

The elemental analysis of the green coloured crystalline compound conforms to the formula Cu(C₃H₆O₂N₂)Cl₂. The molar conductance in methanol shows the complex to be a non-electrolyte. The observed magnetic moment 1.87 B.M. for Cu(II) at room temperature is very nearly the same as the reported value 1.85 B.M. at 300°K for the copper complex of dimethylglyoxime² which is known to be square planar. The diffuse reflectance and solution electronic spectral bands (Table 1) suggest square planar symmetry for the complex³. The intense band observed in 40,000 cm⁻¹ region is probably due to charge transfer transition.

Nickel(II) complex:

The scarlet-red coloured complex having the formula Ni(C₃H₆O₂N₂)₂ arrived at from elemental analysis, appears to be a non-electrolyte from its conductivity in nitromethane. The diamagnetic nature of the complex favours a square planar

TABLE I
ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRA, MAGNETIC DATA AND CONDUCTANCE VALUES OF Cu(II), Ni(II) AND Co(II) COMPLEXES WITH MONOMETHYLGlyOXIME

Compound	Medium	Absorption maxima cm ⁻¹ and molar extinction coefficients (ε)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)	Λ _M mhos
Cu MMG Cl ₂	Diffuse reflectance	25,000; 22,730-19,230; 16,000-13,700.	1.87	48.04 (methanol)
	Chloroform	40,320-40,000(6785); 20,700(70) 13,610-13,520(60)		
Ni(MMG) ₂	Diffuse reflectance	24,390; 22,220-21,550	Diamagnetic	4.78 (nitromethane)
	Chloroform	37,880-37,310(5633); 30,300-29,850(1287); 27,030-26,320(62); 22,730(260); 19,800(70).		
Co(MMG) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ .Cl ₂	Diffuse reflectance Methanol	24,390; 16,000 39,370 (15,880); 22,00sh, 16,000sh; 12820(28); 10,420(11).	1.49	199.80(methanol)

MMG = monomethylglyoxime; sh = shoulder.

NOTES

stereochemistry for Ni(II). The spectral transitions for the complex (Table 1) bear a close resemblance to the bands reported for square planar Ni(dimethylglyoxime)₂ complex.

Cobalt(II) complex :

On the basis of elemental analysis, the reddish-brown complex is assigned the formula Co(C₃H₆O₂N₂)₂(H₂O)₂Cl₂. It appears to be 1:2 electrolyte from its conductivity in methanol. The $\mu_{eff} = 1.49$ B.M. for Co(II) at room temperature is lower than the value 1.7-1.9 B.M. expected for tetragonally distorted octahedral complex. The thermomagnetic data in the temperature range 82°K-295°K rules out the

possibility of exchange interaction between the neighbouring metal ions. The low value may, therefore, be attributed to partial oxidation of Co(II) to Co(III) which is observed in case of ligands containing N atoms as donors⁴. The electronic absorption

Fig 1

Fig. 3.

Fig. 2

spectra (Table 1) do not offer much help in arriving at the stereochemistry of the complex. Livingston and Nolan⁵ have reported a broad reflectance band around 18,000 cm⁻¹ for Co(II) complex with N-(2-methylthiophenyl)-2'-methylthiophenyl methyleneimine which is claimed to be a rare example of low spin octahedral Co(II) complex. The present low spin Co(II) complex appears to possess tetragonally distorted octahedral symmetry.

I.R. spectra :

The characteristic vibrational bands for the ligand and its metal complexes alongwith their probable assignment based on similar assignments by Blinc and Hadzi⁶ are detailed in Table 2.

TABLE 2

I.R. SPECTRA OF MONOMETHYLGLYOXIME AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES (cm ⁻¹)				
M.M.G.	Cu(II) complex	Ni(II) complex	Co(II) complex	Assignment
—	—	—	3400	O H stretch for coordinated water
3250, 3050-2950	3300-3000	3060, 2700-2600, 2400-2300	3270, 3180-3000	Hydrogen bonded NO-H stretch.
1625, 1260	1580, 1250	1555, 1260	1570, 1255	C = N stretch N-O stretch

MMG = monomethylglyoxime.

From the above discussion it can be concluded that the ligand molecule coordinates with metal ions through two N atoms of oxime groups. Copper and Nickel ions form essentially square planar complexes with respect to the coordinating atoms, Co(II) ion has tetragonally distorted octahedral symmetry with water molecules occupying the axial positions and the nitrogen atoms in the equatorial plane.

The probable structures of the three metal complexes suggested on the basis of the experimental data are shown in Figs. 1-3.

References

1. TSOHUGAEFF, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1911, 82, 871.
2. B. N. FIGGIS and C. M. HARRIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 855.
3. R. S. DRAGO and J. T. DONUGHUE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 572; 1962 1, 866.
4. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, 'Advanced Inorganic Chemistry', Interscience Publishers, 1967, 867.
5. S. E. LIVINGSTON and J. D. NOLAN, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 1817.
6. R. BLINC and D. HADZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4536; *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1960, 16, 853.

Electrolytic Reduction of Nitrogen to Ammonia

SANTI R. PALIT

Department of Physical Chemistry,

Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science,
Jadavpur, Calcutta-32.

Manuscript received 28 October 1975, accepted 6 January 1976

NITROGEN is extremely difficult to be reduced under mild conditions though there have been many recent attempts¹ to do so due evidently to its greater technological importance and enzymatic significance. In connection with our work on non-Faradaic electrolysis^{2,3} we have been considering the idea of electrons or H^- or $(H_2O)_a^-$ or similar reducing species being produced near the cathode and migrating towards the anode. We planned to test such a rather unconventional idea by noting whether nitrogen can be reduced near the cathode under conditions favourable to non-Faradaic electrolysis. We have achieved success and this preliminary note reports the same.

Experimental

The experimental arrangement is as shown in Fig. 1. We have chosen distilled water as the electrolyte as this is highly non-Faradaic in current conduction. As a precaution against spurious introduction of electrolytes which may act unfavourably the cellophane is freed of all electrolytes by repeated

washing with refluxing hot distilled water for days before use until the wash water shows no increase of conductivity. On sending a current of the order

Fig. 1.

of 1 mA through this solution for a few hours (preferably overnight), water in the cathode compartment turns deep pink to phenolphthalein. This unmistakably points out that an alkaline substance has been produced in the cathode solution. This turned out to be a mixture of small concentrations of ammonia and caustic soda, the latter being obtained from the sodium ion present in the glass and/or in the cellophane. That this solution contains ammonia as the dissolved base is conclusively proved by the fact that it gives positive reaction with Nessler solution. The Nessler test becomes very strong (precipitation) if the neutralised catholyte is reduced by evaporation to a small volume before testing with Nessler reagent. It is further observed that if dilute sulphuric acid ($\sim N/1000$) is used as the electrolyte, higher yield of ammonia is obtained. That the ammonia is derived from the dissolved nitrogen is proved as follows. Highly purified water which is saturated by bubbling highly purified nitrogen yields ammonia as described above but if water from which the dissolved nitrogen has been boiled off is used in an oxygen atmosphere, no detectable ammonia is formed. It may be mentioned that if the enclosed electrode is the anode, the dissolved nitrogen gets oxidised to nitric acid; details will be published later.

Attempts are being made to scale up the fixation process and increase the yield with a view to effecting direct fixation of nitrogen on a large-scale electrolytically. Further work is in progress to determine the influence of various factors.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Sri Prithwis Kumar Bose for essential experimental assistance.

References

1. G. CHATT and G. J. LEIGH, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 1972, 1, 121.
2. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 636.
3. S.R. PALIT, *Chemistry (Amer. Chem. Soc.)*, 1975, 48, 16.